

Research Libraries, Researchers & the EOSC: Northern European Landscape

*Workshop Report. Written by Camilla
Lindelow*

General notes

This 3rd workshop focused on universities and research organisations from Northern Europe. The target audience was research libraries and researchers.

The workshop programme and information about the speakers, moderator and rapporteur could be found here: <https://www.knowledge.services/research/research-libraries-researchers-and-the-eosc/w3/>

Participant analysis

Excluding the speakers and organiser staff **34 people registered to the event from 34 institutes from 16 countries** with the following distribution: Sweden (9), Bulgaria (1), Germany (2), Netherlands (3), UK (3), Chile (1), Romania (5), Norway (1), France (2), Denmark (2), Ireland (1), Scotland (1), Croatia (1), Finland (1), Italy (1), Moldova (1).

The gender distribution¹ of the 34 attendees was: **12 female (63%), 6 male (32%) and 1 unknown (5% - did not provide a real person name on Zoom).**

The moderator, **Marta Teperek** (Head of Research Data Services at TU Delft Library and Director of 4TU.ResearchData) lead the main room with a gentle hand, keeping the time and choosing questions to be posed from the chat.

We were fortunate to have two of the eight newly elected Directors of the EOSC Association, **Wilhelm Widmark** (library director of Stockholm University) and **Klaus Tochtermann** (Director, Head of Department: Digital Information Infrastructure, ZBW, EOSC Sustainability WG, Kiel, Germany) as presenters. They completed each other well, where Wilhelm focused on the objectives and organisation of EOSC and how the Swedish HEIs are preparing to work with EOSC. Klaus summed up two reports produced within the EOSC project concerning the landscape analysis for a sustainable EOSC, highlighting the important work that has already been done.

The breakout rooms maybe would have benefitted from being even smaller groups to stimulate discussion. Since there is so much to discuss regarding EOSC, the rooms came up with answers to the posed questions from different angles, but the discussion between participants was scarcer. Discussions could also benefit from not having a moderator, as even if this person tries to stay in the background people tend to look for the moderator for answers.

With that said, participants contributed with thoughts on all posed questions. The value of EOSC to researchers and research libraries seems to fall into two main categories:

- the data itself
- the services surrounding it

The highlights

What is the value of EOSC for researchers and research libraries, based on the goals/work of the EOSC?

¹ Assessment was made by the rapporteur based on the participants' first names. Participants were not asked to state their gender during registration/participation.

Engagement!

Figure 1: Engagement! (Denkschets, 2021)

For researchers it will be *one place to go to* for curated data that is *FAIR*, hosted in a sustainable infrastructure and fulfilling legal requirements.

For research libraries it would be a hub to share best practices and skills and training experiences in a way that is scalable and efficient. The participants raise a word of caution though - it all remains to be seen how it works in reality.

What is the input needed from these stakeholders towards of the EOOSC?

The input needed from these stakeholders would be the sharing of experiences and good practices. Trust, coordination and cooperation are also of importance on behalf of the libraries. Uptake and commitment on behalf of researchers. The collaboration between researchers and libraries is also emphasized several times. Input would also be needed on different levels, from local to international. Also for this question the difficulty of giving input before being aware of what's in it is stressed.

How can these stakeholder groups be actively involved in EOSC activities and what do they need to get involved?

Minimum viable EOSC

Figure 2: Minimum viable EOSC (Denkschets, 2021)

The stakeholder groups may be involved in several ways, but clearly relating to the first question answers of data and services. Some argue for the importance of a critical mass of data available for use. Others insist on the sharing of stories and practices. Also the question of Open Education is raised as something to consider as well. When it comes to what they need to get involved in, training webinars and workshops like this is mentioned. There is also a call for working groups under the Association, but also the need to use existing networks such as Liber. The language barrier is also acknowledged, communication is needed in the local languages, as well as the common ones.

What feedback mechanism could be built to continuously inform EOSC, in its quest to remain an agile infrastructure?

In order for EOSC to remain an agile infrastructure feedback mechanisms like user ratings, surveys and monitoring of use should be in place. Open processes where feedback may be given on a draft (like the work with the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda) is also appreciated. Advanced analytics, including AI, are also proposed. The importance of an effective, and at the same time transparent, communication is highlighted.

Most of the participants formulated their thoughts on the questions given. Many universities and university libraries were present, and not just from the Northern part. There were also some participants representing more specialized stakeholders and some actors from the industry as well.

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